

Togetherhood

SPACE X Deliverable, Work Package 5 (D5.6, D18)

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SPACE X Work Package 2: Practices
Secondments: Van Abbemuseum, NN
Contemporary

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Together- hood - eine performative Intervention in Hannover/ a performative intervention in Hanover

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transparadiso realized the performance "Togetherhood" in Hanover: a collective parade through public spaces that brings together local actors from different backgrounds under a silver blanket. In doing so, transparadiso is extending the invitation from the City of Hanover to design an artistic thread through Hanover to the question of how different concepts of art and culture can be linked between the city center and the periphery.

transparadiso invited participants from different districts, backgrounds and institutions to actively participate as performers. "Togetherhood" refers to Leibniz's "Monadology", in which Leibniz states that everything is interconnected. According to Leibniz, there are small units (monads) that are self-contained - but part of a multiplicity. The silver blanket with its 20 hoods, under which the participants slipped, thus became a collective body that, like the multi-faceted eye of a fly, allowed the gaze to wander in different directions. At three stops, "Togetherhood" addressed this ambivalence between microscopic perception and a multi-faceted overview on current issues in social and urban space and made them tangible - in reference to Leibniz's reflections.

Togetherhood

With "Togetherhood", transparadiso staged a parade of silence: pausing, marveling, stillness, resting, and introspection. The performance stimulates a macro-utopian space in multiplicity, in which the "glass ceiling" of power structures and social inequality is questioned and future fictions of communities have space - across borders, despite all the conflicts that currently determine our society and the world. At two stops, visitors following the parade had the opportunity to "swap hoods", i.e. to change under the silver blanket.

"Togetherhood" created an empathetic exchange between different communities, as participatory project - as silent activism.

Togetherhood can be watched here:

<https://vimeo.com/1047888894?share=copy>

The project can be found here:

<http://www.transparadiso.com/en/projects/togetherhood>

Togetherhood was realized in cooperation with:

Obdachlosenchor Hannover (choir of the homeless), Bettina Paletta (freelance dance choreographer), Prof. Dr. Michael Kempe (Leibniz Archive of the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Library in Hanover), Thomas Kaestle (curatorial advisor), Sophie Casna (performer), Kestner Gesellschaft (Adam Budak, director), Literaturhaus Hannover (Kathrin Dimmer, director), Kunstverein Hannover (Christoph Platz-Gallus, director), Staatstheater Hannover (Anne Gruenhagen, et. al.), and many others.

Curatorial advisor: Thomas Kaestle

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<http://www.transparadiso.com/en/projects/togetherhood>